

Sm/TiCl₄ system induced reductive coupling reactions : synthesis of tetraarylfurans

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Induced by low valent titanium, tetraarylfurans have been synthesized in good yields starting from aroyl chlorides under mild and neutral conditions.

Tetraarylfuran is an electron-rich molecule which is widely used as a test in photo-oxidation experiments^{1,2} and as a radical ion precursor in studies of electro-generated chemiluminescence³. Lmpricht and Schwarnert⁴ reported the synthesis of tetraphenylfuran by the reaction of benzoin with concentrated sulfuric acid. Kar and Kar⁵ reported that benzoin could undergo transformation to tetraphenylfuran when refluxed with *p*-toluensulfonic acid in dry xylene with azeotropic removal of water. But numerous byproducts were produced and the yield remained low (*ca.* 25%). Haddadin *et al.*⁶ described the preparation of tetraarylfurans from 2-ene-1,4-diones using trialkyl phosphites as a coupling reagent. This procedure is general, but the required 1,2-dibenzoylstilbene is not readily available and the yield is less than 42% in most cases. Recently, Dams *et al.*⁷ have reported a new route to tetraphenylfuran by reductive coupling of benzoyl chloride with LiAlH₄/TiCl₃ system. Although this route provides tetraphenylfuran in 80% yield, its generality for the preparation of other tetraarylfurans was not demonstrated. Furthermore, this procedure requires large amounts of lithium aluminium hydride and the operation is inconvenient. More recently, Krepski *et al.*⁸ have described the synthesis of deoxybenzoin and tetraphenylfuran by the reduction of benzoin with iodotrimethylsilane. The advantage of this method is its simplicity, but the products are more complicated and tetraphenylfuran is usually the minor product. Our research group found that Sm/TiCl₄ is a highly efficient system for reductive coupling⁹. This prompted us to undertake a more detailed study on Sm/TiCl₄ system. We now wish to report the reductive coupling of aroyl chlorides induced by Sm/TiCl₄.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Tetraarylfurans were prepared from aroyl chlorides with TiCl₄/Sm as the reducing agent (Scheme 1). However, when benzoic acid, methyl benzoate and ethyl benzoate were treated with low-valent titanium in THF at 65° for one day, the yield of tetraphenylfuran was low (25–35%) and benzil (40–45%) and dibenzoylstilbene (10–15%) were formed as well (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

In conclusion, the present work may provide a useful method for the synthesis of tetraarylfuran from the starting materials. This method has some advantages over the existing methods, such as mild reaction conditions, absence of byproducts and better yields over the previous methods.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran was distilled from sodium-benzo-phenone prior to use. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra (CCl₄) were determined on a Bruker AC 80 MHz instrument, chemical shifts being expressed in ppm downfield from internal standard tetramethylsilane. Mass spectra were recorded on HP5989B mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses were carried out on an EA 1110 instrument.

General procedure for the synthesis of tetraarylfuran :

Note

A mixture of Sm powder (2 mmol), TiCl_4 (0.17 ml, 0.22 mmol) and THF (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen, then was cooled to R.T. When black slurry was formed, aroyl compounds (4 mmol) was added in small portions and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. The reaction was quenched with 2 N HCl (10 ml) and the mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 (20 ml) and the organic layer was dried over anhyd. MgSO_4 . After removal of the solvent, the reaction mixture was separated by column chromatography on alumina using petroleum and ether-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) as eluent : **a** (Ar = C_6H_5) (85%), m.p. 172–174° (lit.¹⁰ 173.5–175°), ν_{max} 3040, 1595, 1485, 1440, 1150, 1107, 1070, 1055, 1028, 950, 920, 800, 764, 750, 700, 688 cm^{-1} , m/z 372, **b** (Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$) (86%), 184–185° (lit.⁸ 185–186.5°), ν_{max} 1515, 1495, 1195, 1105, 945, 940, 835, 820, 815, 735, 715 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 2.31 (12H, s), 6.95–7.38 (16H, m), m/z 428, **c** (Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$) (85%), 204–206° (Found : C, 77.81; H, 5.63; $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 78.03; H, 5.73%), ν_{max} 2829, 1585, 1480, 1455, 1230, 1145, 830, 635, 610 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 3.76 (12H, s), 6.70–7.47 (16H, m), m/z 492; **d** (Ar = $p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$) (86%), 206–207° (lit.⁸ 205–207°), ν_{max} 1485, 1080, 1000, 935, 840 cm^{-1} , m/z 510; **e** (Ar = $p\text{-FC}_6\text{H}_4$) (80%), 218–219° (lit.⁸ 219–221°), ν_{max} 1590, 1510, 1490, 1230, 1150, 830, 635, 610 cm^{-1} , m/z 444; **f** (Ar = $m\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4$) (75%), 168–171° (Found : C, 48.65; H, 2.31. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{16}\text{Br}_4\text{O}$ calcd. for : C, 48.88; H, 2.34%), ν_{max} 1590, 1490, 1440, 1230, 1150, 760, 675 cm^{-1} , m/z 668. The yields were based on aroyl chlorides. Other compounds were ben-

zil, m.p. (lit.⁷ 95°) and dibenzoylstilbene, m.p. 212–213° (lit.⁷ 213–214°).

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